

Smart Audio System Based on Voice Command (Sistem Audio Pintar Berasaskan Kawalan Arahan Suara)

Weng Thong Kuan*, Muhammad Faiz Bukhori
Faculty of Engineering & Built Environment, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia

ABSTRACT

There are a wide variety of audio systems available in the market. However, very few of them allow routine user operations such as song selection and volume control via voice commands. Furthermore, they can only play pre-loaded songs, severely limiting the choice of playable music. Voice command is a relatively new technology with many promising applications. The primary aim of this project is to design and develop an audio system capable of voice command control. The central component of this audio system is the single-board-computer Raspberry Pi: its primary function is to run the Speech-To-Text algorithm that records and translates user voice into executable commands, such as “play music” and “volume up”. The Pie also connects to the Internet — and upon user voice commands — could fetch and tell real-time information such date and weather. These features have been successfully implemented in the prototype audio system. In addition, average response time between receiving user commands and executing them has also been measured. SWOT analysis of the prototype has yielded possible areas of improvement, including response time and noise immunity.

Keywords: Audio system; voice command

ABSTRAK

Pasaran mempunyai pelbagai jenis sistem audio. Walau bagaimanapun, hanya sedikit jenis membolehkan operasi pengguna rutin seperti pemilihan lagu dan kawalan kelantangan melalui arahan suara. Selain itu, ia saja boleh memainkan lagu yang pra-dimuatkan. Hal ini telah mengehadkan pemilihan muzik yang dimainkan. Arahan suara adalah satu teknologi yang agak baru dan mempunyai banyak aplikasi yang berguna. Matlamat utama projek adalah merekabentuk dan membangunkan satu sistem audio yang mempunyai kawalan arahan suara. Komponen utama sistem audio ini ialah komputer papan-tunggal, Raspberry Pi. Fungsi utamanya adalah menjalankan algoritma Pertuturan kepada Teks yang merekod dan menterjemahkan pertuturan pengguna kepada arahan seperti “memainkan muzik” dan “meningkatkan kelantangan”. Raspberry Pi juga bersambung ke Internet — dan berdasarkan arahan suara pengguna — boleh mendapat dan memberitahu maklumat masa nyata seperti tarikh dan cuaca. Fungsi-fungsi ini telah berjaya dibina dalam sistem audio prototaip. Di samping itu, purata masa tindak balas antara menerima arahan pengguna dan melaksanakannya juga telah diukur. Analisis prototaip SWOT juga menghasilkan bidang yang berpotensi untuk penambahbaikan, termasuk masa tindak balas dan imuniti bunyi.

Kata kunci: Sistem audio; Kawalan arahan suara

INTRODUCTION

This project is a development project that combines an audio player system with a smart control system based on voice commands. Most of the conventional audio systems in the market use manual operating control systems. System operations such as song selection are manually determined by the user via the keyboard, or buttons with special function. The played audio collection has to be loaded first (pre-loaded), and it will be played repeatedly if the audio collection is not updated. In addition, the audio selection is manipulated manually through the control buttons. Most conventional audio players do not have

automatic control over the audio volume, since they do not account for the surrounding noise that will always change and dynamically. Therefore, users usually have to set their own appropriate audio strength manually via the volume control buttons.

This project will solve these problems by incorporating a smart system into an audio system, which is a characterized audio system like below.

First, system operation can be started and stopped automatically and cyclically, without requiring users to do it manually. After deciding the store hours, the system will switch on the music when the store starts operating and switches off when the store closes. This can save time and

effort of the shopkeeper to open and close the music. Users can turn on the system all the time without the need to turn it off.

Second, the developed system will automatically select and download music from the Internet, based on factors such as the user's music taste, location, weather, time, theme and mood as desired by the users. The selection of music plays an important role in matching the desired themes and goals (Milliman 1986). Other than music chosen by the users, the system will choose the music that is suitable for time-based themes (Edworthy & Waring 2006), weather, and environmental for the users. The system can get information like weather from the internet to make music selection. With this function, unsuitable and unprofessional music selection can be solved.

Third, the system will automatically control audio volume based on surrounding noise. As the number of people grows up or the surrounding noise level increases, the system can automatically increase the volume of music. This ensures the music works well in any situation. When the surrounding noise is reduced, the system will turn the audio volume back to a comfortable level.

Fourth, the system can be controlled by using user voice commands. System operations such as selection of song collection and audio volume can be controlled by user voice commands. Voice command is a relatively new way of control. It is an interesting thing because of its ease and intelligence (Bt Aripin & Othman 2014). Voice commands can be given in multiple forms for different uses and functions. A list of functions and instructions will be programmed and ready for various uses such as operating controls. This also facilitates the addition of functions and controls through upgrading the system over the internet.

Last but not least, users can request the desired music with user's voice. With the use of voice commands, users can choose a particular collection of songs by speech. This speeds up and facilitates users in song selection. If without function of voice commands, users need to enter words one by one with buttons or onscreen keyboard.

METHODOLOGY

In this project, a single-board micro computer, Raspberry Pi (Upton 2014), will be used to connect

to the internet, get necessary information and music from the internet, run programed flow and process user's voice commands (Sachdeva & Katchii 2014). In addition, some other components will be used to support Raspberry Pi in its functions like speakers, microphones, and LEDs. The system operation flowchart is shown in Figure 1.

First of all, Raspberry Pi will play music after being switched on. When the music is playing, the system will check whether the interrupt occurs, which means keyword before the voice command. If there is an interrupt, the system will receive the given voice command. If the instructions are valid, the system will run the instructions.

Valid instructions include stopping music, starting music, changing audio volume, requesting a desired songs collection and changing the music theme. If invalid instructions are given, the system will return to the stage before the interrupt occurred ("Control anything with your voice" n.d.).

Back to the main stream, if there is no interruption after music is over, the system will check the time for the weather check. The period to check weather will be set at once every 2 hours. If it is the time to check the weather, the system will get weather information from internet. After that, the music will change the theme that matches with the weather.

If it is not the time to check weather or after checking the weather, the system will check the time to stop the music. If it is the time to stop, the music will stop and enter into standby stage. If not, the system will just continue the music.

The standby stage is a stage that the music has been stopped and ready for voice command. This stage will always check the opening time and interruption. If an interrupt occurs, the system will run the given instructions through voice command such as "start the music". If no interruption occurred but the time to start the music has arrived, the system will enter the weather check stage and start the weather-themed music at that time.

This system uses a loop flow. It will be repeated in the same cycle without stopping. Therefore, the system can be run automatically without any concern. This system can always be turned on because it can work independently without control. Nevertheless, the users can still change and control it as much as the users want.

FIGURE 1. Operation flow chart of system

The Raspberry Pi is simply connected to a speaker and microphone. Moreover, it also connects to a LED circuit for indicating the status of microphone in receiving voice command. The circuit of the system is shown in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2. Circuit connection of system

SPEECH-TO-TEXT ALGORITHM

Voice commands are working by running a module that is available. Selection of modules is determined by keywords. Therefore, spoken speech should be changed to text so that the system can understand and selects the appropriate module. Spoken speech will be sent to "WitAI". WitAI is a robot with machine learning on the internet. It can convert speech to text like Google does. After that, WitAI will send the translated text to the system and the system may follow the instructions and works ("Natural Language for Developers" n.d.). The flow of this algorithm is shown in Figure 3 (Arthi.J.E & M.Jagadeeswari 2014).

FIGURE 3. Flow of Speech-To-Text algorithm

OTHER ALGORITHM

For text to speech, Raspberry Pi uses "espeak" to execute. It is a downloaded program. It can read out the text with function of espeak. Therefore, the system can give some speech feedbacks to users.

For method of checking weather, WMO (World Meteorological Organization) id has to be set in the system profile to locate the city. System can check weather condition of the city through internet ("Jasper Project" n.d.).

For music player, Mopidy has been used. It can connect to popular music source, Spotify for several of song collection. Mopidy also can perform basic operations like pause music, switch to next song and select music collection. Mopidy also provides library for programming. Since voice commands are applied with select the operation module, the modules can be programmed and include the function of Mopidy ("Mopidy is an extensible music server written in Python" n.d.).

RESULT

Figure 4 shows the prototype of the audio system. The connection is same with Figure 2 and connect to PC. PC is used for observing the running process and debug messages. It is not necessary for users.

FIGURE 4. Prototype of audio system

Figure 5, figure 6 and figure 7 show examples when the system is running. They are debug messages of the running process. In figure 5, the highlighted message is the speech of the system saying. It also shows the system successfully gets the weather information from internet.

Figure 6 shows the process of Speech-To-Text. When users give voice command, system will records and uploads to WitAI for converting into text. The debug message shows the transcribed text after converted and received from WitAI. Then the system will chooses the suitable module based on keyword in the transcribed text.

Figure 7 shows the greeting speech when the system starts up. The speech is programmed in the system and system will reads it out every time the system starts up.

Figure 8 is interface of music player, Mopidy. It shows the songs in list, or other song lists. This can manually controls the music player without using voice commands. However, if without PC, music player can only controlled by voice command. And this is what's the system doing.

Figure 9 shows the status of LEDs. When system is ready to receive voice command, LED turns green. When system is processing the command, LED turns red. This indicator gives feedback to users for users to understand the status of voice commands and give command on the right timing.

FIGURE 5. Checking weather with voice command

FIGURE 6. States of Speech-To-Text

FIGURE 7. Greeting of system when start up

FIGURE 8. Mopidy web client

FIGURE 9. Status of LEDs in two different conditions

RESPONSE TIME

After building the system, the effectiveness is the concern afterward. The response time in giving voice commands to system is one of the main elements. The system will has passive listen for listening to interrupt. Before the passive listen starts, microphone will record and measure the surrounding noise level. After the passive listen started, the threshold will be set slightly higher than the noise. Once a sound or voice is higher than the threshold, the system will considers it as interrupt and checks is it the keyword for activating voice commands. This passive listen has a cycle and keeps looping within it. It will still processes even there is no interrupt and restarts the cycle. The period for passive is measured and shown in Table 1. The longer the period means the system will stay longer time in listening to interrupt.

Beside that, the response time after detected an interrupt or received commands also be measured. After an interrupt is detected, system will analysis the interrupt whether it is the keyword or not. This period will disable the microphone for receiving voice commands. The response time is the time for system to do analysis for the voice as it uploads the voice to WitAI and downloads from it. Therefore, the longer the period, it cause more inconvenience

and less sensitive to interrupt or command as the system is idle.

In addition, active listen time also be measured. When system detected an interrupt and it is keyword for activating the voice command, the system will listens for commands for a period. This is known as active listen. This period has pros and cons in different length. If this period is too short, it will causes users for being too rush when giving voice commands. If this period is too long, the system will be slow in responding the users.

However, the passive listen time and active listen time can be adjusted. The passive listen time was set to 60 seconds and active listen time was set to 4 seconds in the system.

TABLE 1. Few response time of system

Type of response	Test 1 /s	Test 2 /s	Test 3 /s	Average /s
Passive listen time	57.72	57.71	57.70	57.71
Response time	4.82	5.62	5.57	5.34
Active listen time	3.90	3.86	3.90	3.89

PROJECT COST

This project is a product development project. The cost of the project mainly comes from the components for the system. The total cost is RM304.00. The list of components and price are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2. Components and cost

No.	Components	Cost
1	Raspberry Pi 3 Model B+	RM189.00
2	Memory card 32GB	RM60.00
3	Microphone	RM25.00
4	Speaker	RM30.00
5	LEDs, transistors, 5V relay and wires	RM0.00
	TOTAL	RM304.00

CONCLUSION

After implemented all the features into this audio system, this audio system has a few strength. First, voice commands allow easy operation via user voice. Second, there is online music can be searched and played. Third, timer set for turn on and off operations. Fourth, automatic volume control based on surrounding noise. Fifth, automatic song selection based on user preference.

However, it also has its weakness. This system requires internet connection to function. Occasionally, it also meets rare intermittent failures to recognize voice commands.

This project has significant impact to some areas. It is integration with smart home applications. It has great potential to improve and innovate. In future, it will has wide market with huge demands.

This product has some threats. Since it is highly dependent to internet, internet speed will affects the response time of voice commands. Thus, the system becomes slow if internet speed is slow. Beside that, noisy environment also will affects voice recognition.

REFERENCES

Arthi.J.E & M.Jagadeeswari. 2014. Control of Electrical Appliances through Voice Commands. *IOSR Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering (IOSR-JEEE)* 9(1): 13–18.

Bt Aripin, N. & Othman, M. B. 2014. Voice control of home appliances using Android. *Proceedings - 2014 Electrical Power, Electronics, Communications, Control and Informatics Seminar, EECCIS 2014. In conjunction with the 1st Joint Conference UB-UTHM* 142–146.

Control anything with your voice. (n.d.). <https://jasperproject.github.io/> [27 April 2018].

Edworthy, J. & Waring, H. 2006. The effects of music tempo and loudness level on treadmill exercise. *Ergonomics* 49(15): 1597–1610.

Jasper Project. (n.d.). <https://github.com/jasperproject> [27 April 2018].

Milliman, R. E. 1986. The Influence of Background Music on the Behavior of Restaurant Patrons. *The Israel annals of psychiatry and related disciplines* 13(2): 286–289.

Mopidy is an extensible music server written in Python. (n.d.). <https://www.mopidy.com/> [27 April 2018].

Natural Language for Developers. (n.d.). <https://wit.ai/> [27 April 2018].

Sachdeva, P. & Katchii, S. 2014. A Review Paper on Raspberry Pi. *International Journal of Current Engineering and Technology* 381844(66): 3818–3819.

Upton, E. 2014. New product launch! Introducing Raspberry Pi Model B+. <https://www.raspberrypi.org/blog/introducing-raspberry-pi-model-b-plus/> [5 December 2017].